

Research

SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURS ROLE ON POVERTY REDUCTION THROUGH JOB CREATION

Papel Tanchangya*, ***Chu Yingjing***, ***Nazmul Hasan Chowdhury***

School of Business Department, Zhengzhou University, Zhengzhou, China

****Corresponding author***

E-mail: papeltan@gs.zzu.edu.cn

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Abstract: *Social entrepreneurship is relatively a new concept or a new way of doing business which has been gaining a lot of attention in the business world. Not only this concept is being focused by the entrepreneurs, public sector or civil society but also the academic community is paying attention towards this subject through the production of the research paper. This paper is an attempt of creating an understanding towards the role of job creation by social entrepreneurs in reducing the poverty around the world which is a great concern for the nations. Poverty is one of the main challenges in global economic development. United Nations has reported that around 1.3 billion people around the world are multidimensional poor that not only means low income but also another number of indicators such as poor quality of life, poor health, and low-quality education. These indicators are linked with lower income because lower the income lower will be the expenditures. Thus, job creation acts as a path way that ensures the availability of money for the poor people so that they can spend it on their needs especially on the education and health which apparently lead them to have a better quality of life. The researcher has chosen qualitative research design because the nature of the topic in consideration does not incorporate any numerical information that is why the qualitative research design is more appropriate than quantitative design. The findings of the study highlight some ways or strategies that can be adopted by social entrepreneurs in order to increase job creation as well as this study give some useful suggestions than can help the social entrepreneurs to ensure their contribution in poverty reduction.*

Keywords: *social entrepreneurship, job creation, problems, solution, poverty reduction*

Introduction

Social entrepreneurship is comparatively a new concept of doing business which has been gaining a lot of attention in the business world. Formally, this concept has come into existence three decades ago and seems getting spread more all around the world. The social problems such as environmental degradation, marginalisation, and exclusion, overcoming societal issues, job employment and mainly extreme poverty around the world have led to the emergence of the concept of social entrepreneurship. Social entrepreneurship tends to bring social change in the vulnerable and deprived societies through providing the means of financial development and advancing the quality of lives in the form of job creation ¹.

It is argued by the academic scholars that social entrepreneurship plays an integral part in terms of raising the financial improvement with ultimately lowering the poverty index in the vulnerable zones around the world. The existing literature assures that social entrepreneurship makes economic opportunities enable especially for the vulnerable people of the society and hence it creates a massive effect in terms of confrontation of the social and economic issues of any particular community by combining both profitable and social expertise in business and commercial actions. According to Azmat, the growing trend of social entrepreneurship across the world greatly helps in reducing poverty through the creation and provision of jobs as well as it tends to raise the social capital through generating the new social entrepreneurs, new job opportunities, innovative initiatives to develop the society, new institutional forms and so on ².

Job creation is a greater contribution of the social entrepreneurs to reduce the poverty as discussed by Zu that poverty is also caused when the individuals without jobs become unable to earn regular income, therefore, it is believed that the best possible way of helping the poor is the creation of jobs and integrating the poor into the available jobs outside the competitive labour market. For example, the famous and leading social entrepreneurship Bina Swadaya in Indonesia empowers the groups for utilising the resources and for creating jobs through various social

¹ Hussain, M.D., Bhuiyan, A.B., and Bakar, R., 2014. Entrepreneurship development and poverty alleviation: An empirical review. *Journal of Asian Scientific Research*, 4(10), p.558.

² Azmat, F., 2013. Sustainable development in developing countries: The role of social entrepreneurs. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 36(5), pp.293-304.

businesses³. The objective of this organisation is to empower poor people to raise their dignity. Thus, it is often discussed that social entrepreneurship is the great mean of creating jobs for the people in need and it ultimately contributes to reducing poverty. The current research is also an attempt to analysing how social entrepreneurs help in reducing poverty through job creation? Which strategies they can adopt and how they can help the government in ensuring economic development?

Background of the Study

Poverty is one of the main challenges in global economic development. United Nations has reported that around 1.3 billion people around the world are multidimensional poor that not only means low income but also another number of indicators such as poor quality of life, poor health, and low-quality education⁴. These indicators are linked with the low income as Rawhouser, Cummings and Newbert argued that lower the income lower will be the quality of life and standard of living. There are diverse reasons for poverty such as lack of access to adequate resources that result as a difficulty for the poor people to get rid of poverty. Also, poverty is caused by the individuals' inability to achieving the minimum capacity required to gain fundamental freedoms of life, freedom of life in the sense of obtaining economic facilities and availing economic opportunities. If such fundamental freedoms of life are retained by the individuals it will impact the quality of life allowing the people to be free from the poverty line and get escaped from the deprivations⁵.

The empirical researches have demonstrated the significant role of social entrepreneurs, as well as their contributions, has been examined by several scholars. Social entrepreneurship acts as an invisible hand in the economy arose from the concerns and moral commitment of people⁶. The reduction of poverty has become an important consideration for governments because of the

³ Zu, L., 2020. Fostering Social Innovation and Youth Entrepreneurship for the Achievement of the UN 2030 Agenda: The Chinese Way. In *The Future of the UN Sustainable Development Goals* (pp. 341-365). Springer, Cham.

⁴ Wu, J. and Si, S., 2018. Poverty reduction through entrepreneurship: incentives, social networks, and sustainability. *Asian Business & Management*, 17(4), pp.243-259.

⁵ Rawhouser, H., Cummings, M. and Newbert, S.L., 2019. Social impact measurement: Current approaches and future directions for social entrepreneurship research. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 43(1), pp.82-115.

⁶ Ashraf, M.M., Razzaque, M.A., Liaw, S.T., Ray, P.K. and Hasan, M.R., 2019. Social business as an entrepreneurship model in an emerging economy. *Management Decision*.

consequences of poverty. United Nations also took initiative in the form of Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to which organizations in each industry comply with ⁷. Likewise, social entrepreneurship is also an initiative for reducing the poverty as argued by Alvarez and Barney that social entrepreneurs have emerged due to poverty, exclusion, and marginalization in a society which in turn leads to social problems. For overcoming such social problems some people have taken the initiative to tackle the social problems by using a business or entrepreneurial principles ⁸.

This is the contribution of social entrepreneurship for the improvement of quality of life and the sustainability of economic growth. The empirical studies indicate that if social and business skills are incorporated into entrepreneurship activities they help in tackling the economic and social problems in the society and thereby enable economic opportunities particularly for the poor people ⁹. The current study is aimed to examine the possible links with the help of which the social entrepreneurs enable the economic opportunities for the poor thereby combating poverty.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the current study is to find the role of social entrepreneurs (in terms of job creation) to reduce poverty. Further objectives of the study include;

- To determine the strategies that can be adopted for creating jobs and ultimately reducing the poverty
- To provide some suggestions to the social entrepreneurs that can help in poverty reduction
- To analyse the contribution of social entrepreneurs in economic development

Research Questions

⁷ Luke, B. and Chu, V., 2013. Social enterprise versus social entrepreneurship: An examination of the 'why' and 'how's pursuing social change. *International Small Business Journal*, 31(7), pp.764-784.

⁸ Alvarez, S.A. and Barney, J.B., 2014. Entrepreneurial opportunities and poverty alleviation. *Entrepreneurship theory and practice*, 38(1), pp.159-184.

⁹ Thurman, P.W., 2016. *Entrepreneurship and sustainability: business solutions for poverty alleviation from around the world*. Routledge.

The current study is aimed to address the following questions;

- How social entrepreneurs can create job opportunities?
- Which strategies social entrepreneurs can adopt for poverty alleviation?
- How social entrepreneurship can help the government in economic development

Literature Review

The literature on social entrepreneurship is not as vast as on the commercial and conventional entrepreneurial activities because the concept of social entrepreneurship is relatively new in the academic context and therefore it cannot be said that the existing literature on social entrepreneurship is adequate to create an understanding about the phenomena. According to Bielefeld and He the social entrepreneur can be understood as the agents ensuring the change in the existing social factors by bringing the improvements in the social and environmental issues in the societies or communities ¹⁰.

Social entrepreneurship is about saving the community or society from different social problems that affect them. According to Latah social entrepreneurs play a very important role in an economy as they both identify the problem faced by the people and find solutions to the problems. Additionally, the social entrepreneurs incubate innovation along with providing the solution to the societal problems. However, the success of social entrepreneurs can be determined by the achievement of the desired outcomes and fulfillment of the mission. Thus, social entrepreneurs are supposed to create positive social change by providing solutions to the identified societal problems ¹¹.

Lin, Winkler, Wang, and Chen have argued that the role of social entrepreneurs is not limited to the fact of solving the societal problems but their role is far more stretched and wide for covering the indirect benefits of the whole community or society ¹². According to Wang, Duan and Yu social entrepreneurs are also beneficial as they provide other advantages too such as the creation

¹⁰ Bielefeld, W. and He, L., 2012. Social enterprise in China. In *Civil Society and Governance in China* (pp. 111-129). Palgrave Macmillan, New York.

¹¹ Lateh, M., 2018. Social Entrepreneurship Development and Poverty Alleviation-A Literature Review. *MAYFEB Journal of Business and Management*, 2.

¹² Lin, S., Winkler, C., Wang, S. and Chen, H., 2019. Regional determinants of poverty alleviation through entrepreneurship in China. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, pp.1-22.

of employment opportunities for the people of the affected society. Additionally, the social entrepreneurs not only provide job opportunities to the people in need but also it contributes towards the achievement of national identity and thus enhances the economic growth within the country of operation. People on the other hand also get benefitted in terms of personal growth as well as enhanced reputation and recognition of social entrepreneurs in the world through their involvement. It means it is not just the economy that stands to benefits from social entrepreneurs but also the society in general and individuals in particular due to the availability of jobs to them¹³.

Generally in the literature, the role of social entrepreneurs is misunderstood by including only their potential to bring social change that is imparted on the society but the impacts of the of job creation and provision by social entrepreneurs on the individual members of the society are often overlooked¹⁴. It was found that the involvement of individuals in social entrepreneurs enhance their abilities and potentials and provide openness to their career path. They train and develop the employees and increase their experiences which help them to find better job opportunities in the market. Thus, a better job means more spending on the necessities that ultimately enhances the quality of life of the individuals. Researchers view social entrepreneurs as efficient models with the help of which the social needs are addressed¹⁵.

It was noticed that the significant role of social entrepreneurs in alleviating poverty among the non-governmental organisations engaged in microenterprise development. The social entrepreneurs also remain engaged in extending the credit to the owners of small businesses which in result creates employment or job opportunities for the members of the society. The concept of job creation through social entrepreneurship has been gaining more importance especially after the introduction of global goals in which the eradication of poverty is first. Social entrepreneurs work for public goods and try to provide them all the basic facilities such as health

¹³ Wang, C., Duan, Z. and Yu, L., 2016. From nonprofit organization to social enterprise: The paths and future of a Chinese social enterprise in the tourism field. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 28(6), pp.1287-1306.

¹⁴ Qu, T., 2017. Poverty alleviation in China—plan, and action. *China Journal of Social Work*, 10(1), pp.79-85.

¹⁵ Bruton, G.D., Ahlstrom, D., and Si, S., 2015. Entrepreneurship, poverty, and Asia: Moving beyond subsistence entrepreneurship. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 32(1), pp.1-22.

care which brings improvements in the life of the people and they contribute in the economic development of the country by providing their maximum potential in the business operations ¹⁶. Over the last decade, the unprecedented growth and development of social entrepreneurs can be observed worldwide. This mode of business has been gaining attention not only by the government but also by the corporate sector through the sustainability of the economy and social dilemmas remain the major concern of the social entrepreneurs. The data in Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) report reveals that social entrepreneurship activities are globally emerging at a very faster rate as compared to commercial and conventional endeavor¹⁷. It has also been observed that social entrepreneurs act as a great source of ensuring economic development in the country because they tend to identify as well as reduce various societal problems. However, there is still a need for an effective institutional framework and regulatory support to the social entrepreneurs so that they can thrive in the entrepreneurship sector ¹⁸. Zhang, Zhou, and Lei have explained that social entrepreneurship is a discipline that has been generating social impact by adopting the entrepreneurial approach. Their study investigated social entrepreneurs and their contributions to economic development and growth. The theoretical analysis in the literature also suggest that the social entrepreneurs are very essential for economic development and contribute significantly in the local economies especially through the job creation and improving the quality of life of the people as well as by providing the valuable social services to the local people of the community ¹⁹. The potential of the social entrepreneurs for contributing to economic growth is largely dependent on the broader system of different layers of the community for influencing and increasing the impact as a change agent. That is why social entrepreneurs must be included in the process related to economic activities such as in doing business, policy designing and so on ²⁰.

¹⁶ Wu, J., Zhuo, S. and Wu, Z., 2017. National innovation system, social entrepreneurship, and rural economic growth in China. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 121, pp.238-250.

¹⁷ Zaefarian, R., Tasavori, M. and Ghauri, P.N., 2015. A corporate social entrepreneurship approach to market-based poverty reduction. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 51(2), pp.320-334.

¹⁸ Macke, J., Sarate, J.A.R., Domeneghini, J. and da Silva, K.A., 2018. Where do we go from now? A research framework for social entrepreneurship. *Journal of cleaner production*, 183, pp.677-685.

¹⁹ Zhang, Y., Zhou, X. and Lei, W., 2017. Social capital and it's contingent value in poverty reduction: evidence from Western China. *World Development*, 93, pp.350-361.

²⁰ Pathak, S., and Muralidharan, E., 2018. Economic inequality and social entrepreneurship. *Business & Society*, 57(6), pp.1150-1190.

However, the government and legal bodies are also responsible to provide basic policies for the social entrepreneurs and assure the availability of the legal measures for creating an appropriate environment for the social entrepreneurs' growth that will ultimately affect the social entrepreneurship sector in the society. There is a need of creating a favourable legal context for the social entrepreneurs where they will be treated similar to the commercial business organisations²¹. According to Saebi, Foss and Linder social entrepreneurs focus on inclusive growth which means the poor members of the society who are not involved in the economic activities benefit from the economic growth through the participation in a way that the factors such as job creation is accurately factored into economic processes such as in conducting business, in policymaking and in designing the financial policy. Social entrepreneurs embody the ideal of social objective that generates social impact through incorporating the employment entrepreneurial approach²².

It is further believed by the researchers that social entrepreneurship can become the catalyst for changing economic power structures and thus it can become a game-changer for the economic transformation at the broader level. Social entrepreneurs have potential to significantly increase their economic and social impacts to become the long-lasting change agents. Thus, the social entrepreneurs tend to contribute more in identifying and solving the societal problems and to help the government to ensure the economic development in the country²³.

Methodology

This study employs qualitative research design and entirely focuses on secondary data. The researcher has chosen qualitative research design because it tends to describe the phenomena in more details as compared to the quantitative type of study. Further, the nature of the topic in consideration does not incorporate any numerical information that is why the qualitative research design is more appropriate than quantitative design²⁴. Qualitative research design is also

²¹ Si, S., Yu, X., Wu, A., Chen, S., Chen, S. and Su, Y., 2015. Entrepreneurship and poverty reduction: A case study of Yiwu, China. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 32(1), pp.119-143.

²² Saebi, T., Foss, N.J. and Linder, S., 2019. Social entrepreneurship research: Past achievements and future promises. *Journal of Management*, 45(1), pp.70-95.

²³ Pathak, S. and Muralidharan, E., 2018. Economic inequality and social entrepreneurship. *Business & Society*, 57(6), pp.1150-1190.

²⁴ Quinlan, C., Babin, B., Carr, J. and Griffin, M., 2019. *Business research methods*. South-Western Cengage.

employed when the research is aimed to create an understanding related to the phenomena in a social and real context. The current study seeks to analyse the role of social entrepreneurs in terms of job creation to reduce the poverty and poverty is typically a social problem so understanding the role of social entrepreneurs in reducing such social problem through job creation is an ultimate objective of the study which can be understood by employing qualitative research design.

Qualitative research design can be understood as the scientific method of observation for gathering non-numerical data. Walliman has discussed that the qualitative research design provides an overview of the related topic through existing researches to assess which aspects have been covered in previous studies, which aspects are still needed to be considered and how can the research gap be filled. It is also believed that qualitative research design also provides new perspectives related to the topic as well as the openness of data can be ensured by employing qualitative research methodology. With the help of qualitative research design, the researcher can convey his findings in a better, deeper and in an understanding way ²⁵.

This study is aimed to understand the role of social entrepreneurs in poverty reduction. The plethora of existing researches on the given topic has helped the researcher to find new ways of defining the problem. The researcher has collected the data by considering empirical evidence and research papers. Such researches help in deriving the most relevant and appropriate information to explain the topic into consideration ²⁶. All the findings of the study have been supported by empirical evidence. Hence, the current study is an attempt that seeks to extend the existing literature by creating an understanding of the purpose of social entrepreneurs and their respective roles in the reduction of poverty. The current study uses interpretivism as a philosophy of research in which the researcher interprets the findings and information collected from the existing literature ²⁷.

Findings

The findings of the current study are divided into four parts reflecting the answers to the research questions discussed above. The literature on social entrepreneurship shows that social

²⁵ Walliman, N., 2017. *Research methods: The basics*. Routledge.

²⁶ Flick, U., 2015. *Introducing research methodology: A beginner's guide to doing a research project*. Sage.

²⁷ Silverman, D. ed., 2016. *Qualitative research*. Sage.

entrepreneurs are the great source of job creation and poverty alleviation but the question arises that how such jobs can be created by the social entrepreneurs or which strategies they can adopt to create jobs for reducing the poverty and for eliminating the poverty from the country ²⁸. The subsequent sections provide answers to such concerns.

7.1 Job Creation through Social Entrepreneurship

Social entrepreneurs firstly create a shared value rather than just profit. It all starts when social entrepreneurs start realizing the need for bringing improvements and betterments in society. Social entrepreneurs put one eye on the community they live in and focus on the individuals whose lives need to be improved. They tend to recruit locally and choose those who struggle to prove their selves or who seek to have a job. The existing literature shows that social entrepreneurship initiatives are taken to solve social problems such as poverty by building on local capacities. Social entrepreneurs remain engaged with their local communities and use their knowledge and networks for finding solutions to the problems faced by poor communities. Social entrepreneurs attempt to create employment opportunities particularly for poor people like low-qualified people or people with any disability who are usually excluded from the labour market. Social entrepreneurs set their mission to involve the poor people in productive and economic activity which not directly helps them to make their lives better as well as benefits the economy of the country. The work integration social entrepreneurs (WISEs) are aimed to integrate the excluded members of the society who seek to work by involving them in a productive activity ²⁹.

For example, ‘The Specialists’ which is a for-profit consultancy firm from Denmark that usually and exclusively hires autistic people. This entrepreneur ensures that more people with autism will be more likely to have employment in the firm. Similarly, Amul in India is another example that leverages the social landscape to create employment and to promote socio-economic development. The milk production sector in the company employs the family labour which the poor had amply. The main aim of the company was not to eradicate the problems of poverty and unemployment but now it has become the agenda of the company and it has impacted millions of

²⁸ Light, P.C., 2011. The search for social entrepreneurship. *Strategic Direction*, 27(6).

²⁹ Defourny, J. and Kim, S.Y., 2011. Emerging models of social enterprise in Eastern Asia: a cross-country analysis. *Social enterprise journal*, 7(1), pp.86-111.

landless small farmers also the company played a significant role in generating the employment for the poor women of India. These examples represent that how companies intentionally or unintentionally get involved in creating the job opportunities for the vulnerable people of the society by focusing on the people whose lives need to be improved and who should be provided the opportunities to make their lives better.

7.2 Strategies to be Adopted by Social Entrepreneurs

Social entrepreneurs can be taken as an unparalleled catalyst for bringing social change and economic development. By using market-driven strategies they tackle a critical social issue in brand new ways. The common way adopted by social entrepreneurs to reduce poverty is job creation. The social entrepreneurs can employ many strategies for creating jobs and ultimately for the reduction of poverty. For example, social entrepreneurs can identify a viable opportunity arising from crisis-oriented and vision-oriented factors. They can create jobs with a clear social mission of ensuring employment in a particular community. Social entrepreneurs can firstly start with a promising idea that is usually generated by recognising the social needs, social change, and social assets, as well as the social entrepreneurs, will have to ensure that whether this promising idea can be transformed into an opportunity. The social entrepreneurs need to have a compelling social impact theory and a plausible business model which in result helps in generating viable job-creating strategy.

According to Xiaohong, social entrepreneurs can adopt two major strategies for creating jobs such as the establishment of new social entities or expansion of social entrepreneurs. The social entrepreneurs can convince the governmental bodies to support them in terms of related reforms and policies and can ask the financial institutions for the funding. The social entrepreneurs can establish new social entrepreneurs but they should be based on a market-centered business model not wholly but partially because separating the social entities from the mainstream of economic context of the country can become a threat to the image of social entrepreneurship³⁰. The social entrepreneurs can also expand their operations but again financial support is necessary to fund such operations. Thus, the first step for the social entrepreneurs is to considerably recognise the need of employment for the people of the country as well as it should adopt market-centered

³⁰ Xiaohong, W.M.Z., 2010. An Outline of Social Enterprises [J]. *China Nonprofit Review*, 2.

business model because combining the social work with purely entrepreneurial activities can help the companies to accomplish their mission of job creation and poverty eradication.

7.3 Suggestions for Social Entrepreneurs

The concept of social entrepreneurship is relatively new in the ways of doing business and it has been becoming more common around the world but there is lacking from the government side which restrains the social entrepreneurs to achieve their mission of serving the social problems along with generating profit. The entrepreneurial activities of for-profit firms have many supporting policies and legal measures but social entrepreneurs still do not have legal and governmental support. That is why it is suggested to the social entrepreneurs to collaborate with the governmental and regulatory bodies to get an appropriate environment for social entrepreneurs development. It is also suggested that the social entrepreneurs in the collaboration of each other should ask the regulatory bodies to create a favourable legal context where the social entrepreneurs should be treated similar to the other commercial entrepreneurs. The emerging and developing countries are specifically suggested to adopt the model of the Low-profit Limited Liability Companies (L3Cs) in US and Charitable Incorporated Organisations (CIOs) that were instituted mainly to provide support social entrepreneurs ³¹.

The social entrepreneurs can present their plan of solving the specific social problems such as poverty to the government in effective ways. They can meet the government representatives and concerned authorities to convince them to make supporting reforms for the social entrepreneurs. Similarly, social entrepreneurs can also request the public authorities to compensate the social entrepreneurs in the form of provision of the fiscal advantages. The fiscal advantages if granted by the public authorities to the social entrepreneurs it can contribute to the public interest and well-being of the poor communities as social entrepreneurs tend to minimise the collateral costs to the society. The social entrepreneurs should also ensure the negotiations with the institutions regarding the access of equivalent financial markets similar to medium and small-sized entrepreneurs regardless of the goals and missions of the social entrepreneurs. They should

³¹ Siu-Lun, W., 2017. Chinese entrepreneurship and economic development. In *China After Socialism: In the Footsteps of Eastern Europe or East Asia?* (pp. 130-148). Routledge.

effectively present their mission statement to the financial markets to assure financial assistance from them.

It is further suggested that the social entrepreneurs should not solely focus on the governmental policies but also they should bring changes in their pension fund policies like an investment of minimal percent of the money in social entrepreneurs can also help the social entrepreneurs in scaling up their activities and increase their impacts globally. Also, the social entrepreneurs should ensure that they are not positioning their entities outside the mainstream economy because it has been observed by the researchers and scholars that social entrepreneurs generally seek to have solutions of their challenges by creating new separate social institutions such as social venture capital, social stock exchange or social legal entity which is very difficult to achieve.

Therefore, social entrepreneurs should focus on being complied with the mainstream economy by assuring the changes in the existing institutional framework. If social entrepreneurs position their selves as a separate entity they might decrease their attractiveness for the commercial businesses to be engaged with them and will, therefore, the potential of the social entrepreneurs will remain limited for becoming a catalyst for economic transition. Another change that is highly suggested to the social entrepreneurs is that they should integrate the ideas of creating the social value in business within the core business' curriculum and should not isolate the sector from the mainstream economic business research. This can trigger the growth of the social entrepreneurs' sector and also can make it successful enough for raising the consumer expectations for increasing the market returns to the social responsibility.

7.4 Role of Social entrepreneurship in Economic Development

It is commonly believed by the researchers and academic scholars that social entrepreneurs have the potential to solve several social problems faced by the people around the world especially by those who belong to the lower-income class. Social entrepreneurship can eliminate the problems by contributing to the economy such as social entrepreneurs work for the public good. Unlike commercial businesses, they think beyond the profit generation and try to help the people in need

in the economy ³². According to Eldar, the economic development of any country is represented by the respective GDP, life expectancy, per capita income, poverty level, and many other indicators but the human development index has also been the part of economic development indicators. Human development means the overall achievement of any particular country in its economic and social dimensions. Such dimensions are based on the health of the individuals, the education level, and material living conditions, access to food, shelter, quality of life and their standard of living ³³.

Zahra and Wright discuss that these dimensions are linked with the income. If people have money to spend other than on necessities they will have better educational status, good health, more life expectancy, a better standard of living and a high quality of life. Income is largely dependent on the availability of jobs and job creation is the main focus of social entrepreneurs. Job creation ensures the engagement of individuals in any economic opportunity which brings improvements in human development index on one hand because social entrepreneurs usually seek to employ those people who are suffering vulnerable conditions of living and who are the neediest people for the job ³⁴. On the other hand, it helps the government to boost economic development because it contributes to the reduction of poverty and any country cannot become developed until it reduces poverty to the maximum. Social entrepreneurs not only serve the people for good but also generate profit which means a significant contribution of the sector in the country's GDP ³⁵.

The governments of any country usually remain considerable to find ways of minimising the societal and economic problems and to enhance economic development. Social entrepreneurs can play a significant role in both regards but they are needed to be provided the financial support from the concerned departments similar to the commercial businesses along with the effective institutional and regulatory framework for social entrepreneurs. They can help the country in

³² Nicolás, C. and Rubio, A., 2016. Social enterprise: Gender gap and economic development. *European journal of management and business economics*, 25(2), pp.56-62.

³³ Eldar, O., 2017. The role of social enterprise and hybrid organizations. *Colum. Bus. L. Rev.*, p.92.

³⁴ Zahra, S.A. and Wright, M., 2016. Understanding the social role of entrepreneurship. *Journal of Management Studies*, 53(4), pp.610-629.

³⁵ Huysentruyt, M. and Stephan, U., 2017. Social enterprises, an economic force for building more inclusive societies? Evidence from the SEFORÍS study.

enhancing the GDP, reducing the poverty, increasing the quality of lives of the people, ensuring the fulfilment of the necessities of people by creating and providing the jobs to the people in need. Social entrepreneurs also ensure the flow of social capital in the economy that can be used to implement sustainable economic development of the country ³⁶.

The social entrepreneurs also act as an alternative to the market-centered development model of business and put emphasis both on profit generation and social development in the country. Through job creation, social entrepreneurs act as role models that motivate the people to come forward and bring positive change in the societal setup. These entrepreneurs address the severe global problems such as poverty, inadequate education, poor health, unemployment, etc. by allowing the poor people to get access to the money in the country and fulfil their needs and wants ³⁷. Once they become able to enhance their quality of life, the economic development of the country ultimately gets ensured. For example, all the member countries of the United Nations have been directed to ensure sustainability on a global pace for which the governments have been taking several measures to ensure the fulfilment of targets set in SDGs by the UN. Government is seeking to ensure the economic development, higher quality of life, a higher level of education, good health of people and mainly its first goal is about the eradication of poverty which can be achieved by the contribution of the social entrepreneurs ³⁸.

Conclusion

The current study concludes that social entrepreneurs play a significant role in poverty reduction as well as economic development. The study discussed the role of social entrepreneurship in job creation which ultimately helps in poverty reduction. The study also discussed some strategies such as expansion or introduction of new social entities that can be adopted by the social entrepreneurs to grow the social entrepreneurs in the world. The study also provides some suggestions to the social entrepreneurs regarding collaborating with the governmental and regulatory bodies to have an institutional framework for social entrepreneurs as well as they must

³⁶ Sengupta, S., and Sahay, A., 2017. Social entrepreneurship research in Asia-Pacific: Perspectives and opportunities. *Social Enterprise Journal*, 13(1), pp.17-37.

³⁷ Sengupta, S., Sahay, A. and Croce, F., 2018. Conceptualizing social entrepreneurship in the context of emerging economies: An integrative review of past research from BRICS. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 14(4), pp.771-803.

³⁸ He, C., Lu, J. and Qian, H., 2019. Entrepreneurship in China. *Small Business Economics*, 52(3), pp.563-572.

ensure that social entrepreneurs are being treated similarly as the commercial entrepreneurs are treated by the government and the legal context. It was also suggested that social entrepreneurs should not solely focus on governmental policies but also they should bring changes in their policies to scale up their activities and increase their impacts globally. The social entrepreneurs also act as an alternative to the market-centered development model of business and put emphasis both on profit generation and social development in the country. Through job creation, social entrepreneurs act as role models that motivate the people to come forward and bring positive change in the societal setup. Thus, the social entrepreneurs if bring improvements in their policies they can foster their growth in the world and can help the countries to tackle the social problems from a broader perspective.

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3. Zu, L., 2020. Fostering Social Innovation and Youth Entrepreneurship for the Achievement of the UN 2030 Agenda: The Chinese Way. In *The Future of the UN Sustainable Development Goals* (pp. 341-365). Springer, Cham.
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5. Rawhouser, H., Cummings, M. and Newbert, S.L., 2019. Social impact measurement: Current approaches and future directions for social entrepreneurship research. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 43(1), pp.82-115.
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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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